

 Cite this: *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.*, 2019, 21, 17441

DOI: 10.1039/c9cp90188d

rsc.li/pccp

Correction: Understanding the role of co-surfactants in microemulsions on the growth of copper oxalate using SAXS

 Sunaina,^{ab} Vaishali Sethi,^c Surinder K. Mehta,^b Ashok K. Ganguli^{*c} and Sonalika Vaidya^{*a}

 Correction for 'Understanding the role of co-surfactants in microemulsions on the growth of copper oxalate using SAXS' by Sunaina *et al.*, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.*, 2019, 21, 336–348.

The authors would like to make readers aware of an error in the published version of this manuscript. In Fig. 11, all the reflections except the most intense peak had been marked as (020) which was a typographical error.

The correct figure with *hkl* values inserted is presented below (Fig. 11). There are no changes to the conclusions of the manuscript as a result of this correction.

Fig. 11 PXRD pattern of copper oxalate monohydrate obtained via the reverse micelle method in the case of (a) 1-butanol and (b) 1-octanol as the co-surfactant.

The Royal Society of Chemistry apologises for these errors and any consequent inconvenience to authors and readers.

^a Institute of Nano-Science and Technology, Habitat Centre, Phase – 10, Sector – 64, Mohali-160062, India. E-mail: svaidya@inst.ac.in

^b Department of Chemistry and Centre for Advanced Studies in Chemistry, Panjab University, Chandigarh-160014, India

^c Department of Chemistry, Indian Institute of Technology, Hauz Khas, New Delhi-110016, India. E-mail: ashokganguliitd@gmail.com

